

Technical Note: The six Layers of Protection in Fire Engineering

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The resulting fire risk is part of how safety is implemented in a building via the layers of fire protection. These are 6 layers in their simplest form and in approximate chronological order: prevention, detection, evacuation, compartmentation, suppression, and structural resistance. The layers aim to reduce the fire risk of a building, with five of the layers aiming to reduce fire severity, while prevention reduces fire likelihood. All layers of protection interact with one another and in general, if one layer is breached, another layer can compensate and mitigate the severity. There are superlayers of protection, such as building regulations or fire brigades, that act on multiple layers at once, hence their importance. The Swiss Cheese model of risk is applied in Figure 1 to the layers of fire protection in a building.

Figure 1 – The Swiss Cheese model of risk is applied here to the different layers of fire protection in a building. A hole in one layer of protection can be compensated by one of the other layers to mitigate the risk. Only when multiple layers are breached (the holes lining up) will a fire become severe. Superlayers, like fire brigades and building regulations, act on multiple layers at once.

The six layers of fire protection can be explained as follows:

- **Prevention** works by understanding the causes of fire, growing awareness of fire safety, and keeping ignition sources away from flammable items. The objective of this layer is to avoid any ignition in the first place. When this layer is breached and a fire takes place, the other layers are given a chance to act.
- **Detection** works by sensing the fire early, its smoke or its heat, such that sounding the alarm gives occupants time to act while the fire is small. Detection is critical for evacuation, manual suppression, and calling the fire brigade, which are in the next layers.
- **Evacuation** works by conducting the safe egress of the occupants from the path of the fire and the smoke. It is of critical importance to life safety and requires routes of escape to safer areas. First evacuation is from the room of origin, further evacuation can be partial, phased, or complete. The faster the detection and the better the compartmentation, the more time is available for safe evacuation. The fire brigade can contribute by coordinating the evacuation and rescue.
- **Compartmentation** works by restricting fire growth through the walls and ceilings of the building, creating compartments, and containing the fire close to its origin. Openings in the walls, such as doors, windows, and ducts, can be fire resistant to avoid a breach of the layer. Stopping external fire spread and the spread from building to building are also part of this layer.
- **Suppression** works by extinguishing the fire or greatly slowing down its spread. Means of suppression include manual extinguishers or automatic suppression systems, such as sprinklers or systems that flood an area with inert gases. The fire brigade also aids in fighting the fire and preventing its spread. Smoke ventilation can be seen as part of this layer or as part of compartmentation.
- **Structural resistance** works through strengthening the building to sustain loads during the fire. Fire weakens the strength of materials and creates additional forces and displacements within the building structure. The structure therefore requires adequate design to prevent collapse and must stand safe while occupants and fire brigades are inside.